

Arts in Education in France: State of the Art & Best Practices

National Report Summary

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Arts Education in France: State of the Art & Best Practices

2016

the government rolled out the Charter for Artistic and Cultural Education

50 million

French Ministry of Culture budget cut (in 2025)

57%

of students accessed a cultural and artistic educational action vs. 39% for schoolchild

OVERVIEW

In France, the national ambition of art through education is to offer equal and diversified access to artistic and cultural practices, to encounters with artists and to works of art, with the aim of supporting emancipation, inclusion and citizenship. However, in spite of this institutional commitment, there are disparities and much more complexity regarding the current contribution at every level. Plus, digital technologies challenge the relationship to education. Thus, in an age of increasingly powerful digital technology and the proletarianization of knowledge, what about art in lifelong education as a mean of empowerment in France?

This summary provides a brief overview of findings from institutional reports and documents, academic readings and discussions with groups of experts (education professionals, artists and associative project leaders).

KEY FINDINGS

Policy Strengths:

France has a multiplication of national schemes to facilitate access to culture for all young people. Firstly, in 2016 the government rolled out the Charter for Artistic and Cultural Education to lay the foundations for Cultural and Art Education. In addition, there is the Pass Culture scheme, which is intended to support the actions of the government's EAC charter. The Pass Culture aims to contribute to “the generalization of artistic and cultural education (EAC)”. There are also artists' residencies in schools and extracurricular activities, such as those run by Ateliers Médicis, which are another way of combining educational and cultural activities. This enables students to enjoy immersive experiences, which help to anchor EAC in the local area, often across disciplines and in conjunction with local cultural players. Finally, there's an openness to transdisciplinarity, with a cross-disciplinary approach and an openness to innovative practices such as edutainment.

Structural Weaknesses:

First and foremost, there is a lack of harmonization between education authorities, local authorities and cultural organizations. This lack of harmonization often makes it difficult for those working in the art and education to understand what's going on. We have also identified that territorial and social inequalities persist, despite the political impetus given to art and culture in education. In addition, the government seems to maintain a hierarchization of arts and culture while they should be used as a means of transmission and civic expression.

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This summary contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

CRITICAL CHALLENGES

Systemic Challenges

- To give even access to cultural structure and space of expression to all.
- To switch art in education from a consumerist orientation to a contributive and capacitating one.
- To acknowledge art and cultural expressions of all forms.

Operational Challenges

- To articulate the recognition of aesthetics, imaginaries, intersectional justice and interculturality, art, through education, must contribute to the deconstruction of hierarchies by valuing all form of expression.
- To support local associations that relay art and culture as they are crucial for local dissemination.

BEST PRACTICES SPOTLIGHT

A best practice is from the association Citoyenneté Jeunesse, which base its cultural educative activities on 3 pillars:

- **DO**, a collective artistic practice or project that enables participants to explore a creative process, build their self-confidence, develop their creativity and sensitive intelligence, and improve their listening skills and respect for others.
- **SEE**, seeing and observing works of art, and sharing sensitive proposals such as those found at exhibitions or live performances, opens up to other practices, ways of doing and thinking, making cultural venues their own and, more generally, opening up to the world.
- **EXCHANGE**, there are times for meetings, verbalization and exchange within the projects, which can be individual or collective. This enables participants to enrich and exchange their knowledge, support their judgments, argue and share in a calm atmosphere.

ACADEMIC CONSENSUS

In Jeux, gestes et savoirs published by IRI in 2024, the Institute questions the pharmacology of playing as a gesture for self-development between rules and free expression. In the article "Ensemble, on joue", Morgane Balland states that free play fosters autonomy, cooperation and creativity, but excessive supervision can limit its effects. Play is a relational practice that requires a benevolent framework. It must not be reduced to a strict educational purpose.

STRATEGIC RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Educational sciences and art: dialogue between creation, pedagogy and situated knowledge

- polysemy, through devices such as metaphor, analogy or ambiguity;
- an intimate dialogue between body and creation, between time and space.

2. Game, play and education

- Play as social act.
- Importance of co-construction and adaptation of rules to facilitate self-development.
- Risks associated with institutionalizing play as it can lose its substance.

3. Cultivating the posture of the amateur

- There are amateurs of science and technology, just as there are amateurs of art.
- The figure of the amateur is opposed to the figure of the consumer.

4. Exploring new media: video games and critical learning

- enhance technical skills: use and understanding of video game mechanics;
- enhance pedagogical skills by integrating video games into educational contexts to teach geography.

5. Acknowledge cultural diversity

- To develop project-based pedagogy to connect classroom activities with real-world cultural experiences.
- To design pathways that provide continuity across educational levels and personal experiences.

6. Connect with local structures

- The CNAM-INSEAC report points out that associations are key players in cultural mediation and individualized support, helping to build bridges between populations and legitimizing their cultural and artistic experiences, practices and expressions.

CONCLUSION: THE OPPORTUNITY AHEAD

This report intended to make a study of the state of the arts and best practices on arts in education. We identified that the french government has a multiplication of national schemes to facilitate access to culture for all young people. The CAE Charter is a major example of how France try to facilitate art in education. Therefore, we've identified that territorial and social inequalities persist, despite the political impetus given to art and culture in education. Thus, by articulating the recognition of aesthetics, imaginaries, intersectional justice and interculturality, art, through education, must contribute to the deconstruction of hierarchies by valuing all form of expression. Also, local associations play a decisive role in relaying art and culture, the literature and the various local initiatives we've introduced above showed us that they are a key actor to enroll in art and education project.

We want to emphasize that it is necessary to develop the figure of the amateur or the "intermittant" as it is "the ideal-type of the contribution economy" (Stiegler). By switching art in education from a capitalistic orientation to a contributive and capacitating one, we might improve and renew cultural awareness and expression.

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